

Annotating Formulaic Language in 12th Century Papal Charters

Observations on Definitions and Challenges

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Abstract

The system of papal delegated jurisdiction played an important role in enforcing papal judicial primacy from the end of the twelfth century onwards. We aim to investigate the evolution of specific judicial formulaic expressions accompanying this newly emerging type of jurisdiction and therefore address the challenge of annotating relevant expressions in our charter corpus in order to compile a ground truth for the training and evaluation of digital methods for the detection of formulas. By using double blind annotation, we iteratively refine our annotation procedure as well as our working definition of the phenomenon, thereby also discussing problems pertinent to other types of formulaic language such as variable elements and modifications as components of the expressions. Finally, we also present some quantitative observations about the formulaic expressions in the charters annotated so far.

1. Delegated Jurisdiction and Formulaic Language

The system of papal delegated jurisdiction allowed the pope to exercise judicial authority even in remote regions of catholic Europe and thus played an important role in enforcing papal judicial primacy from the end of the twelfth century onwards.¹ The emergence and expansion of this jurisdictional system during the early twelfth century were not only accompanied by a consolidation of the legal procedures itself, but also by a standardisation of the structure and wording of the papal charters functioning as mandates for the judges delegate. While this domain-specific formulaic language has been researched extensively regarding the fully developed *formulae* seen in papal formularies since the 13th century,² the early development of judicial formulaic expressions has been less investigated.

¹ Cf. Müller, “Omnipresent Pope”, 210–218; cf. Herde, “Papal Formularies”, 223–224.

² Herde, *Audientia*; Herde, “Papal Formularies”.

The DFG-funded project ‘Delegierte Gerichtsbarkeit auf der Iberischen Halbinsel im 12. Jahrhundert. Struktur und computergestützte Analyse eines urkundlichen Massenkörpus’,³ carried out by a group of researchers in Digital History (Chair of Digital Humanities, University of Passau) and Papal History (Göttingen Academy of Sciences and the Humanities in Lower Saxony), aims to contribute to the investigation of these early formulaic expressions used in connection with papal delegated jurisdiction on the Iberian Peninsula during the twelfth century. We use methods from text mining and historical network analysis to analyse formulaic language as well as interpersonal networks as reflected in papal charters from that time and region. A carefully conducted manual annotation of formulaic expressions in a subset of our corpus of charters is an important prerequisite for the optimisation as well as systematic evaluation of any methods used to automatically identify and categorise such expressions in unseen documents of the corpus.

In this conference paper we present our approach to the annotation of formulas in medieval papal charters and discuss problems pertaining to formulaic language in general, such as linguistic variance, standardised modifiers, and non-formulaic additions in formulaic expressions. To our knowledge there has been no research so far regarding the systematic manual annotation of the phenomenon in diplomatic language, and since the annotation of formulaic language in general and historical formulaic language in particular for the purpose of computational text mining has seldom been tried, no real annotation standards exist in this field.⁴ We use double-blind annotation to refine our initial annotation workflow as well as to gain a deeper understanding of the structure and characteristics of the judicial formulas related to papal delegated jurisdiction. Since we are especially interested in tracing the stages through which certain expressions became the standardised, fully developed *formulae* known from later letters of justice – or the stages through which they faded from diplomatic language and were abandoned in favour of other expressions – we prioritise

³ ‘Papal-delegated jurisdiction in the Iberian Peninsula in the 12th century. A computational analysis of legal and procedural consolidation based on a large corpus of medieval papal documents.’

⁴ Filatkina, *Historische formelhafte Sprache*, 176: “Für die Annotation formelhafter Wendungen fehlen jegliche Standards”. Approximate translation: ‘No standards of any kind exist for the annotation of formulaic expressions.’. Filatkina presents a workflow for the recording of instances of formulaic expressions (ibid., 165–177), but her procedure aims at facilitating research in corpus linguistics and not at the creation of annotations that can be used as gold data for, e.g., Machine Learning. Koolen and Hoekstra (“Detecting Formulaic Language”, 139) and Leclercq and Kestemont (“Distant Diplomats”, 223–224), all dealing with premodern administrative texts, used digital approaches for the extraction of relevant phrases as an exploratory tool, so that a quantifiable evaluation of the approach itself through a previously defined gold standard was not strictly necessary.

the functionality of formulaic expressions over their exact wording. Therefore, the annotation labels represent the mutual function of a group of formulas which may differ in wording. Examples for frequent formula types can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1a. Annotation example for a text chunk containing multiple short formulaic expressions. The green boxes show the labels (i.e., functions) assigned during annotation and the texts below show a standardised wording associated with this label.

Figure 1b. Annotation example for a text chunk containing two independent formulaic expressions, with one (shown in orange) comprising the shorter expression (shown in blue) and also non-formulaic variable elements as specification.

The text corpus (Iberia Pontificia/IbePon corpus) that forms the basis for this annotation and our consequent analysis consists of ca. 200 papal charters newly edited in the context of the project, as well as of ca. 1000 papal charters from retro-digitised volumes of the series ‘Papsturkunden in Spanien’ (PUU 1–3; English: ‘Papal charters in Spain’)⁵ and two additional volumes of editions.⁶ The newly edited charters will be published as digital edition and as volume four of the mentioned series (PUU 4). While they will incorporate detailed, manually curated information about charter type, actors and places, the retro-digitised charters will be semi-automatically enhanced with structured information by using, e.g., Named Entity Recognition. Part of the digital edition of PUU 4 is also the annotation of judicial formulaic expressions facilitating future research in this area as well as a first study of the phenomenon in the context of the project. The

⁵ Kehr, *Papsturkunden in Spanien: Katalanien*; id., *Papsturkunden in Spanien: Navarra und Aragon*; Berger, Herbers and Schlauwitz, *Papsturkunden in Spanien: Kastilien*.

⁶ Erdmann, *Papsturkunden in Portugal*; Mansilla, *Documentación Pontificia*.

manual annotations will serve as ground truth for the training and evaluation of computational methods for the detection and analysis of formulaic language applicable to the retro-digitised charters.

In the following chapter, we first present our approach to developing annotation guidelines that result in consistent data useful for the investigation of formula-development. In chapter three, we give a working definition of judicial formulaic language in papal letters of justice, which draws on observations made during the development of these guidelines. We discuss challenges pertinent to the annotation of formulaic language in general in chapter four. Finally, we present first observations about the amount and nature of formulaic expressions contained in our corpus.

2. Double-Blind Annotation as Learning-Process

As stated before, no standards for the annotation of formulaic language exist – and any standard of this kind probably would not be universally applicable due to the variance of characteristics between formulaic language in different domains, such as journalism, literature, or in our case: medieval legal documents.⁷ Furthermore, definitions of formulaic language in general and *formulae* in charters in particular vary,⁸ especially in terms of length as well as linguistic and functional standardisation needed to acknowledge some word or sequence of words as formulaic. An under-specified definition makes it hard to spot the phenomenon in texts and to annotate relevant passages in a consistent manner, with different annotators often marking different words while seeing the same expression or not recognising a formulaic expression at all. Therefore, to approximate a consistent and unambiguous *modus operandi*, we decided to use double-blind annotation for a sub-sample of newly edited letters of justice, aiming at an iterative refinement of the underlying definition of judicial formulaic language in this source type as well as our annotation guidelines.

We annotated 17 charters from the second half of the 12th century (popes Adrian IV., Alexander III, Lucius III, Clement III, Celestine III) in four iterations, with eight charters being annotated twice to measure the direct effects of a major change in annotation

⁷ Cf. the annotation approach of Dobrovoljc, „Annotating“, for formulaic sequences in spoken Slovenian. The categories applied here aim at linguistic insight and are only useful when formulaic expressions are identified by frequency instead of domain-specific function and when incomplete syntactic structures (e.g., ‘that they’) may be seen as formulaic. An adaptation for the investigation of formulaic language as cultural (not linguistic) phenomenon in domain-specific historical sources seems impracticable.

⁸ Cf. Fichtenau, “Urkundenformeln”, 286; Herde, “Formel”; Schmitz, “Formel”; Härtel, *Urkunden*, 274; Vogtherr, *Urkundenlehre*, 77–78; Filatkina, *Historische formelhafte Sprache*, 164.

procedure, resulting in a total of 25 annotation samples. The annotation was done by two of the co-authors who also prepare the edition of PUU 4 and are experts in the field of papal history and diplomatic. INCEpTION was used as annotation tool.⁹ In the beginning, the annotators had the task of marking formulaic expressions that they knew from literature, as well as those that they considered to be recurring formulaic expressions according to their expertise. After each annotation round the agreement was calculated and we discussed any patterns of disagreement, adapting the task description as well as annotation guidelines accordingly to be used in the next round. This double-blind annotation was carried out until substantial agreement was reached and the discussion of the results showed that remaining uncertainties could better be addressed by a reviewed instead of parallel annotation.

Table 1: Overview of the batch-size, label set and main annotation guidelines of each annotation iteration with agreement values (Cohen's Kappa=CK) regarding the concrete formula labels assigned to each token (label-wise) and regarding whether a token has been marked as belonging to a formulaic expression at all (binary).

It. No.	No. of charters	Size of label set	CK label-wise	CK binary	Main annotation rules
1	6	84	0.16	0.49	- Expressions categorised according to wording - Labels selected according to known <i>formulae</i> ; complemented by new labels, if needed, according to the expertise of the annotators - No further rules
2	6	69	0.42	0.71	- Expressions categorised according to function - Introduction of a detailed predefined label set - Modifiers annotated separately - No annotation of variable elements - Possibility of annotating parts of expressions separated by insertions
3	5	69	0.43	0.67	- Expressions categorised according to function - Modifiers included directly in the expression's annotation span - No annotation of variable elements - Possibility of annotating parts of expressions separated by insertions
4	8 (already used in i1 [6] and i2 [2])	55	0.72	0.85	- Expressions categorised according to function - Modifiers included directly in the expression's annotation span - Possibility of annotating parts of expressions separated by insertions - Refined label set

An overview of the annotation rounds and their agreement values are shown in Table 1. In the fourth iteration the annotators reached an agreement (Cohen's Kappa) of 0.72 regarding the different labels and of 0.85 regarding tokens being marked as belonging to a formulaic expression (disregarding the exact label of this expression). This is a clear gain in agreement compared to the first round, which had agreement values of 0.16 and 0.49 respectively. The most important changes in annotation procedure were the shift from wording-based to function-based annotation, the use of a standardised

⁹ INCEpTION (Klie et al.) was used as an annotation tool.

label set instead of relying solely on the knowledge of each annotator as well as the introduction of the possibility to annotate expressions as multiple parts, if their relevant words are interrupted by a longer insertion.

The label set compiled so far is quite extensive, with currently 55 different groups of formulas identified, each group representing a special function, that means a certain legal act or concept connected with the expressions in this group, such as ‘to open a trial’, ‘to fix a date’, ‘making a reservation of contumacy’, or ‘to impose ecclesiastical sanctions’. We call these ‘formula groups’, since they can incorporate several formulas of different wording but similar meaning. The set needed constant readjustment, with new formulaic expressions occurring and some already registered expressions proving to be used exclusively with a similar function, thus being merged into one label. This volatility of labels is likely to continue during the annotation of new charters, especially since we are also interested in less standardised expressions, which may occur only a few times in the IbePon corpus. Compiling a definitive set of judicial formulaic expressions is therefore not only difficult to achieve but might not even be helpful in terms of understanding this linguistic phenomenon inherently open to lexical and syntactical variation.

During our project, all other letters of justice edited in the context of PUU 4 will be annotated. While the guidelines of the last test round will be used for this, they might still be adapted to deal with expressions not yet considered. Finally, the annotated charters can be used for the assessment of methods used to identify and analyse formulaic expressions in the non-annotated part of the IbePon Corpus.

3. A Working Definition

Since, as described above, the task of defining formulaic language is not trivial, we find it useful to present the working definition we apply in our research, which was shaped by the observations made and discussions led during the annotation training. Obviously, charters are a highly formulaic type of documents, and formulaic expressions as well as the standardised formal structure of medieval papal, royal, episcopal or private charters have been researched extensively.¹⁰ In our research as well as in the remainder of this paper we focus especially on formulaic expressions that are inherent to papal letters of justice, of which many pertain to judicial processes

¹⁰ E.g., Fichtenau, “Urkundenformeln”; Kortüm, *Urkundensprache*; regarding judicial formularies from the 13th century onwards Herde, *Papal Formularies*.

carried out by judges delegate. We define judicial formulaic expressions in papal charters as multiword expressions, that are employed repetitively in a standardised linguistic form and that carry a certain judicial meaning in the context of papal delegated jurisdiction.¹¹ They have a text- as well as process-structuring function¹² by addressing common elements of a conflict and the corresponding process of its resolution.

While a certain amount of standardisation is necessary to characterise an expression as formulaic, linguistic variance per se is no contraindication for the identification of two differing expressions as one type of formulaic phrase. Three main types of modification can be observed: First, different occurrences of an expression can use differing lexemes or syntax, but still be linked through direct synonyms or paraphrasing and a common meaning (e.g., *appellatione remota*, *appellatione cessante*, and *sine appellationis obstaculo*, preventing the litigants from filing an appeal). Second, formulaic expressions might be modified by additional elements, which are themselves formulaic in the sense that they occur repetitively in a similar linguistic form (e.g., *per apostolica scripta mandamus, quatinus*, where *per apostolica scripta* is a reference to the papal charter itself which can but does not have to be made). And third, formulaic expressions may occur with or without variable elements, that are not formulaic in their wording, but often contain explanations and specifications or help to preserve the style and grammatical structure of a sentence (cf. Fig. 1b). Often, these variables might be needed for the semantic integrity of the expression, as in *si non omnes his exequendis potueritis interesse, [n] uestrum ea nichilominus exequantur* (where *[n]* denotes the minimal number of judges needed to proceed with a trial) or *causa, que inter X et Y vertitur* (where *X* and *Y* as parties of the conflict and the conflict itself can be specified in varying levels of detail). In this sense formulaic expressions can be subdivided into a formulaic core (whose concrete occurrences in charters may differ by wording but not in meaning) and formulaic modifiers as well as non-formulaic variable elements, also called variables.¹³

We furthermore distinguish *formulae*, i.e. the Latin term already used in diplomatic, as a special case of formulaic expression, with *formulae* being such expressions that

¹¹ Cf. Filatkina, *Historische formelhafte Sprache*, 164: 'holistisch' – 'holistic'.

¹² Cf. *ibid.*; Koolen and Hoekstra, "Detecting Formulaic Language", 131.

¹³ Cf. the '<VAR>'-token used by Koolen and Hoekstra, "Detecting Formulaic Language", 130, 144 or the 'insertion of names, placenames or dating' into fixed boilerplate texts as noted by Herde, "Formel".

introduce and contain interchangeable instructions for certain higher-level stages of a process (comparable with the diplomatic parts of a charter, such as *narratio*, *dispositio*, *sanctio*, etc.). The two main stages are, first, the initial appeal to the pope, corresponding to a description of the case in the charter's *narratio* (e.g., *ad audientiam nostram pervenit, quod* – it came to our attention, that), and second, the delegation of the case to judges delegate (e.g. *causam discretioni vestre duximus committendam*) and the execution of the process according to the pope's instructions, corresponding to the dispositive core of the charter, normally introduced by *mandamus* (*atque precepimus*), *quatinus* (we command [and instruct], that). The charters often contain a third section as part of the *dispositio*, which comprises instructions to be taken in certain possible circumstances, e.g., if one of the judges is unable to attend the process (*si non omnes...*, see above), if a party fails to appear in court (*si autem pars se contumaciter absentare presumpserit*), or if a party files an appeal (*si qua vero partium duxerit appellandum*). Following these introductory expressions, certain instructions for how to handle each process stage (e.g., by sending the testimonies of witnesses back to the pope: *attestationes testium [...] apostolicae sedi transmittere*; without obstruction: *occasione et excusatione cessante*; by receiving an oath: *iuramento recepto*; etc.) are given in formulaic form, but the selection, ordering and specification of these instructions might vary. As will be seen, the linguistic as well as structural variability of the formulaic expressions poses a special challenge to their identification and annotation.

4. Challenges in Annotation

The test annotations done so far drew the attention to several overarching challenges regarding the annotation of formulaic language in general and of those in papal charters in particular. First, the question was posed, whether to annotate expressions according to function or according to wording. As described above, the words used may vary, and in addition, some expressions differ substantially, so that they might not be considered the same formulaic expression, even though they have the same function (e.g., *conquestus est nobis, ad audientiam nostram pervenit, significante venerabili fratri nostro accepimus, quod* – all referring to the pope gaining knowledge about some conflict). Furthermore, our goal is not only to look for already known expressions, but to investigate their evolution and to consider stray formulaic phrases, that might have existed temporary but were abandoned too soon to become really

standardised and thus have slipped the attention of research so far. Therefore, to rely on the wording itself would defy the goal of our analysis and we decided to give the same annotation label to expressions with similar meaning or function respectively, seeing them as part of the same group of formulas.

Second, the linguistic variance as well as the formulaic modifiers and non-formulaic variables posed a challenge to the determination of the boundaries of a formulaic sequence of words. On the one hand, it is not favourable to limit the analysis to the part of an expression that we defined above as formulaic core. On the other hand, ascertaining what is part of an extended expression (be it as modifier or variable) proved to be difficult and error-prone when attempted during annotation itself. Since the amount of standardisation – whether something occurs frequently as a special modifier or semantically needed variable, or whether it is an arbitrary addition in this special case – is only apparent when looking at a number of occurrences of the same expression and its contexts, it is nearly impossible to determine the relevance of certain variations in an annotation scenario, where the annotators only ever look at one character at a time. Developing a full classification system for the annotation would result in a large label set – which is prone to inconsistent use due to its complexity – and would – again – require a certain amount of already identified occurrences of formulaic expressions, so that frequently observed variations can be evaluated.

We therefore decided to use a two-step approach. First, we limit our annotation to the labelling of a formulaic expression containing core lexemes as well as possible modifiers, but without variables. To this end we also allow for expressions separated into smaller parts by bigger insertions, which are then linked to mark them as belonging to the same formulaic phrase (cf. Fig. 1b). Otherwise, many annotations would include whole sentences due to the complex grammatical structure of Latin, overarching smaller, independent formulaic expressions, while at the same time failing to point out the part of the sentence, that constitutes the expression that the annotator wanted to mark. Later, using the results of this first annotation, the occurrences of each expression as well as their respective contexts can be examined in detail regarding the frequency of certain lexemes to reveal common modifiers and patterns of variables, which might then be used, if appropriate, to ameliorate the gold standard annotation.

5. Quantitative observations

After discussing the annotation of formulaic language in charters from a wider perspective, we will now present concrete observations on the judicial formulaic expressions in our corpus. For this we draw on the charters annotated during the iterative creation of the annotation guidelines. Since they represent only a small sample with a regional bias towards the dioceses of León and Salamanca, whose charters were the first to be edited for PUU 4, as well as a temporal bias towards the second half of the 12th century, these observations can only be preliminary.

Table 2: Overview of the number of formulaic expressions found by each annotator per annotation iteration, as well as the number of unique labels (i.e., formula groups) assigned to them. The number of judicial formulaic expressions excludes those not specific to letters of justice (e.g., honorifics, papal self-designation).

It. No.	No. of charters	No. of labels assigned		No. of expressions annotated as formulaic		No. of judicial expressions annotated as formulaic ¹⁴	
		Annotator 1	Annotator 2	Annotator 1	Annotator 2	Annotator 1	Annotator 2
1	6	36	37	59	72	59	53
2	6	23	24	85	88	59	57
3	5	34	31	96	82	64	49
4	8	33	35	137	136	96	97

Table 2 shows the number of expressions and formula types (labels) found per annotation round. The recall of separate instances of expressions is substantial with 9 to 13 judicial formulaic expressions found in one charter per average. Interestingly, the number of distinct labels is always much smaller than the size of the label set (cf. Table 1) and exhibits less variation than the number of expressions: In round four, nearly the same number of labels was assigned as in round three, even though more charters were annotated during round four. This might suggest that a set of established expressions was used in most of the charters which would be backed up by the observation of earlier research, that the process of delegated jurisdiction was already relatively standardised by the end of the pontificate of Alexander III.¹⁵ Yet, since the samples are very small, this hypothesis requires future validation with more data. Among the most frequent expressions in our test sample are those that we defined above as *formulae*, introducing the description of a conflict or its delegation, but interestingly also expressions concerning the interdiction of appeal, the imposition of

¹⁴ Expressions not specific to letters of justice (e.g., honorifics, papal self-designation) are excluded.

¹⁵ Müller, "Omnipresent Pope", 215; Herde, "Papal Formularies", 223–224.

ecclesiastical means of coercion or the papal authority given to the judges, hinting at the importance of the corresponding elements in a trial.

Figure 2: Boxplot of the average token length of formulaic expressions (micro-averaged per formula group) found in annotation iteration one (i1) and four (i4).

As already stated, most of the formulaic expressions in the charters are rather short. This becomes clear in Figure 2, where iteration 1 (i1) exhibits a much wider range of values than iteration 4 (i4). In i1 the annotation guidelines did not yet allow for the annotation of separate parts of the same expression. Accordingly, the outliers of 30 words or more represent expressions whose formulaic nucleus is very short (e.g., *causam committere*, to commit a case to a judge), but which can be supplemented by very long additional explanations (e.g., which case, led by which litigants, about which issue of conflict, etc.). In i4, those additions were excluded from annotation so that the boxplot shows only the length of the relevant lexemes constituting the formulaic character of the sentence. Consequently, the remaining outliers represent expressions that already were quite fixed at the time of the charter's issuance and comprise whole standardized sentences, such as the *formulae* found in relevant studies by the name of *Quod si non omnes* or *Testes autem*.¹⁶ The plots also illustrate that an automatic detection of the judicial formulaic expressions observed in our corpus cannot merely rely on the detection of recurring n-grams, since 50% of all length values in i4 lie beneath the length of five tokens. The short n-grams needed to find these expressions

¹⁶ Cf. Herde, *Audientia* 1, 199–200, 219–221.

6. Summary and Future Work

In this conference paper we described an iterative approach to the creation and amelioration of guidelines for the annotation of formulaic language as well as the problems arising during this task. Furthermore, we gave a detailed working definition of judicial formulaic expressions in medieval papal charters and presented first quantitative observations about this special subtype of formulaic language.

While this paper represents work in progress, it might nevertheless be relevant for other researchers trying to annotate formulaic language in historical sources, since several phenomena and challenges that we encountered seem to pertain to formulaic language in general. Among these are what we call modifiers and variable elements, which seem to be essential components of more complex expressions, as well as the fact that formulaic expressions are difficult to detect manually without having a general overview about the whole corpus.

In future work, we plan on annotating all newly edited charters to establish a broader basis for quantitative analysis as well as to use them as gold data for the training and evaluation of methods applicable to the detection and analysis of formulaic language in the non-annotated, retro-digitised part of the IbePon corpus. Promising methods might be Text Reuse Detection,¹⁷ classifiers based on Large Language Models (LLM), or other approaches tailored specifically to the historical sources at hand.¹⁸ Finally, we will combine the gained data about the distribution and evolution of formulaic expressions in our corpus with socio-geographical data to investigate the possible interplay between social or regional groups of actors and their role in the formation of formulaic language related to papal delegated jurisdiction.

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¹⁷ Cf. Leclercq and Kestemont, “Distant Diplomats”, 223–224.

¹⁸ Cf. Koolen and Hoekstra, “Detecting Formulaic Language”.

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